

The Internal Structure of Photon (Graviphoton)

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INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of quantum field theory, the photon is traditionally described as point-like particle without any internal structure^[1]. However, this view does not align well with his behavior and characteristics. To address these inconsistencies, various theories have been proposed. Preonic models have been explored since the 1970s^[2]. Similarly, solitonic and string-based^[3] approaches have attempted to reproduce the observed properties. In this context fits the The Electrogravitational Theory, which posits that the photon is composed of two elementary electric charges of opposite sign^[4], separated by a distance equal to the Planck length l_p . In this case, the Planck length does not represent the distance below which the very notion of space ceases to exist, but rather the binding distance between the two elementary electric charges constituting the photon. The electromagnetic wave is therefore a probability wave, indicating where the photon is most likely to be found. Moreover, since the electromagnetic wave carries energy, a corresponding gravitational wave is associated with it. In this way, the photon and graviton represent two aspects of the same particle, the graviphoton. The two-charge structure of the photon provides an explanation for Planck's relation, its electrical and gravitational properties, the transformation of matter into photons (with all particles, elementary or not, thus composed of elementary electric charges), and it also offers a possible explanation for the composition of elementary particles (which, given that they can be transformed into photons, are therefore also composed of elementary charges^[4]).

THE INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF PHOTON

Consider a plane electromagnetic wave $\vec{A}(x, t) = \vec{A}_0 \sin(kx - \omega t)$ described by \vec{E} and \vec{B} propagating along the x -axis, where \vec{A} represents the electric field \vec{E} or the magnetic field \vec{B} , k is the wave number and $\omega = ck$ the angular frequency. The electromagnetic stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}^{EM}$ associated with this wave contains quadratic terms E^2, B^2 and $\vec{E} \cdot \vec{B}$ oscillating in the upper half-plane as $\sin^2(kx - \omega t)$. Since electromagnetic energy is always positive, the gravitational field associated with the electromagnetic wave is therefore always negative, i.e., attractive

(oscillating in the lower half-plane, *Fig.1*). The quadratic nature of electromagnetic energy with respect to the fields \vec{E} and \vec{B} thus transforms a spin-1 wave into a spin-2 spacetime perturbation. To the electromagnetic wave with periodicity 2π is associated a gravitational wave $\vec{g}(x, t) = -\vec{g}_0 \sin^2(kx - \omega t)$ with periodicity π (*Fig.1*). Here, \vec{E} and \vec{B} are the electric and magnetic fields, while \vec{g} and \vec{K} are the gravitational and co-gravitational fields. The existence of the co-gravitational field \vec{K} is predicted both by linearized general relativity and by gravitomagnetic theory [5].

Fig.1

In summary, every electromagnetic wave has an associated gravitational wave. This demonstrates that electromagnetic waves have a dual “electrogravitational” nature. Using the description of the photon as composed of two electric charges forming a dipole, it is possible to derive the relationship that links its energy and frequency [4].

$$E = \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\mu_e G K}{2c^3} \left(\frac{q_e^2}{l_S} \right)^2 v = \mu_e c \frac{q_e^2}{2\alpha} v = \frac{Z_0 q_e^2}{2\alpha} v = hv \quad (1.1)$$

Here $h \approx 6.626 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s}$ is the Planck constant, Z_0 is the impedance of free space, $\alpha \approx 1/137$ the fine structure constant, $q_e \approx 1.6 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ C}$ is the elementary charge, μ_e is the magnetic permeability, K is the Coulomb constant, G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light, and l_S is the Stoney length, where $l_S = \sqrt{\alpha} l_P$.

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